

Tracing Settlement Dynamics in Latium Vetus: explainable machine learning perspectives from the Bronze to the Early Iron Age

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Abstract

Understanding the long-term drivers of settlement location requires disentangling ecological constraints from historically contingent choices. Here we apply a Random Forest machine-learning framework, coupled with explainable AI techniques, to investigate settlement dynamics in Latium Vetus (central Italy) from the Early Bronze Age to the early Iron Age (c. 2100–725 BCE). Using 110 securely dated sites and a set of environmentally constrained pseudo-absence points, we model phase-specific patterns and evaluate predictor importance through both normalized split frequencies and SHAP values, capturing structural roles as well as the magnitude and direction of effects. The results reveal a coherent diachronic transformation in the environmental logic of settlement. Early phases are primarily structured by hydrological accessibility, whereas from MBA3 onwards topographic configuration and elevation progressively dominate, marking a shift towards morphologically distinctive and defensible locations. This transition culminates in highly canalised settlement signatures during the Final Bronze Age and RMCA phases, before the RMCA III phase signals a landscape that is increasingly saturated, hierarchically organised and functionally diversified, despite overall political stability. While the reliance on pseudo-absences and uneven sample sizes constrain predictive robustness, the approach demonstrates the value of Random Forest and SHAP as exploratory tools to expose non-linear, threshold-like relationships and to formalise long-standing archaeological interpretations. The study shows how explainable machine learning can provide a quantitative backbone for reconstructing the emergence, consolidation and transformation of territorially structured landscapes in protohistoric central Italy.

Introduction

The area roughly bounded by the Tiber, the Aniene river, the initial foothills of the Apennines, and Monte Circeo traditionally corresponds to the region defined by ancient authors as *Latium vetus* or *antiquum* (Plin. *nat.* 3.56; Strabo 5.3.4; Serv. *ad Aen.* 1.6). Although the exact boundaries of this area vary according to different ancient sources (and their precise definition is beyond the scope of this paper), it was traditionally considered the homeland of the *Prisci Latini* or *Casci Latini* (Enn. *Ann.* 22 Sk.) and broadly coincides with the territory characterized, at the transition from the Bronze Age to the Iron Age, by the archaeological facies known as Roma-Colli Albani (Müller Karpe, 1959; Peroni, 1996). Given that this region essentially constituted the formative ground from which Rome subsequently emerged, it has long attracted considerable

scholarly attention within classical and prehistoric research. Emphasis has been placed on understanding its socio-economic dynamics, often starting from the analysis of settlement patterns and associated necropoleis, with different approaches (Alessandri, 2013; Bietti Sestieri, 1984; Carandini, 1997; Cornell, 1995; Fulminante, 2023, 2014; Guidi, 2024; Holloway, 1996). If we consider settlements as agents acting upon a stage defined by the landscape, understanding their behaviour necessarily involves identifying the reasons behind their foundation in a specific location. These motivations must, by definition, be rooted in the characteristics of the chosen site. However, once such features have been identified, one is confronted with the challenge of determining which among them were essential, influential, or negligible in the settlement decision-making process. To address this, and beyond relying on informed intuition (which, although valuable, is not easily quantifiable) the approach has primarily involved the use of statistical methods. For instance, by comparing expected versus observed settlement locations in relation to their distance from specific landscape features, such as rivers, springs, or bodies of water (Alessandri, 2013). The aim of this contribution is therefore twofold. First, it seeks to explore the application of a Machine Learning algorithm, the Random Forest (Breiman, 2001), in assigning importance values to these variables (for a similar approach, but applied to a different dataset and using partly different scoring metrics, see Cardarelli, 2023). Second, it aims to evaluate the results considering previous research.

Geographical and chronological boundary

The area selected for the application of the method corresponds to only a portion of what was traditionally considered Latium Vetus. Specifically, it encompasses the region between the Tiber and Aniene rivers, the Astura River, and the sea, that is, an area including the so-called Roman countryside (Campagna Romana), the Alban Hills (Colli Albani), and the coastal zone to the south of the latter (Fig 1). The exclusion of the southernmost part of Latium Vetus (the Pontine Plain and the Volscian Mountain range) was a methodological necessity to ensure data quality for Machine Learning. The Pontine Plain is a largely buried alluvial landscape where prehistoric sites are geologically obscured, while the Volscian range remains largely unexplored. Including these areas would have introduced a systematic "missing data" bias (false absences correlated with specific environments).

The dataset

The study area, initially only partly, and later entirely under the control of early Rome, has long attracted archaeological investigation (Fig 2, caption with bibliographic references). Research has varied widely in both scope and methodological rigour, and has been conducted over a period of more than a century (Alessandri, 2013; Belardelli et al., 2007; Gierow, 1966). Eleven volumes of the *Forma Italiae* series cover sectors wholly or partially falling within this region (Fig 2, 2-10, 13, 16). Although invaluable as topographically organised inventories of documented archaeological evidence, these catalogues do not represent systematic, landscape-scale surveys.

Systematic fieldwork was undertaken only in the early-1980s within the municipality of Rome, yet most of the resulting dataset remains unpublished (Fig 2, 1). More recently, the Groningen Institute of Archaeology has carried out small-scale systematic surveys within restricted sectors as part of successive research programmes (Fig 2, 11, 12, 14, 15). Outside these limited areas, available information largely derives from incidental discoveries, such as those recorded in the early twentieth century on the Alban Hills during large-scale vineyard development.

As a result, the statistical representativeness of this archaeological record remains uncertain. However, unlike the Pontine Plain and the Volscian range, where the paucity of data derives from structural invisibility of the evidence (buried landscapes) or lack of systematic exploration, the Campagna Romana–Alban Hills–coastal sector constitutes the only portion of Latium Vetus in which archaeological visibility is sufficiently

homogeneous and the archaeological record is sufficiently documented to allow meaningful comparison between environmental parameters. Furthermore, the massive urban and infrastructural expansion of the Rome metropolitan area has necessitated decades of systematic archaeological monitoring, although conducted with uneven intensity and methodological standards over time. This development activity cuts across all landscape types indiscriminately, valleys, hillslopes, and plateaus, effectively generating a large, quasi-random sample of the archaeological record (Fig 3).

The aim of this study is therefore not to reconstruct the settlement history of the entire region, but to apply an exploratory model only where the archaeological signal is robust enough to make such comparison interpretable.

The chronological span considered here begins with the Early Bronze Age and extends to the end of the Roma-Colli Albani III phase. Thus, it covers a chronological range from approximately 2100 to 725 BCE.

The chronological phases are abbreviated as follows; all dates are approximate and given in BCE.

- Early Bronze Age – EBA (2100-1700);
- Middle Bronze Age, subphases 1 and 2 – MBA12 (1700-1400);
- Middle Bronze Age, subphase 3 – MBA3 (1400-1300);
- Recent Bronze Age – RBA (1300-1150);
- Final Bronze Age, subphases 1 and 2 – FBA12 (1150-1050);
- Final Bronze Age subphase 3, (also Roma-Colli Albani I) (1050-950);
- Roma-Colli Albani IIA – RMCAIIA (950-880);
- Roma-Colli Albani IIB – RMCAIIB (880-800);
- Roma-Colli Albani III – RMCAIII (800-725).

Methods

Settlement parameters

The environmental variables influencing the establishment and long-term viability of a settlement in a given location are multifaceted; for the purposes of this study, the following were assessed: topographic setting, absolute altitude, distance from the sea, from rivers, from freshwater bodies (such as lakes and lagoons), and from springs. The amount of land more or less suitable for agriculture, arboriculture, and pastoralism has also been considered, within a one-hour walking radius from the settlement's center (Fig 4). The model evaluates locations as if they were independent, and does not account for inter-site competition or territorial exclusion, which may have influenced the realised settlement pattern in densely occupied phases.

With regard to the topographic setting, the categories are defined as follows (within the RF model, each category is represented by a number, shown here in parentheses):

- Isolated peak (1): an isolated elevation whose maximum height, relative to the surrounding landscape or to the nearest higher saddle, exceeds 40 m;
- Plateau (2): a flat or gently undulating surface bounded on at least three sides by steep scarps;
- Ridge (3): an elevation that is isolated on only two sides;
- Slope (4): non-isolated areas with moderate, steep, or very steep inclines ($>10\%$);
- Hill (5): an isolated elevation whose maximum height, relative to the surrounding landscape or to the nearest higher saddle, does not exceed 40 m;
- Plain (6): non-isolated areas that are flat or gently sloping ($\leq 10\%$).

Distance is expressed in minutes of walking time (expressed in hundredths of a second to obtain only integer values; for example, a value of 6000 corresponds to one minute of walking time), calculated using the Naismith's rule (Langmuir, 1984; Naismith, 1892), an empirically derived algorithm that models human movement as a function of slope frequently employed in archaeological studies (Alessandri, 2016a, 2016b; Pažout and Eisenberg, 2021). The algorithm was implemented using the `r.walk` module of GRASS within QGIS 3.40 (Bratislava). The Tobler function does not incorporate additional variables that likely influenced mobility, such as vegetation, watercourses, or soil type. It provides a reasonable approximation, appropriate for the scope of this study. Distance calculations are based on a 20 m resolution DEM, derived from a landscape reconstruction of Latium Vetus during the Bronze and Iron Ages proposed by Alessandri (2013). This reconstruction integrates geological and pedological maps, pollen and radiocarbon data, and, where available, historical cartography. Springs are taken from Ventriglia (1990) and represent the modern hydrography. As such, they offer only an approximate indication of those available in protohistoric times. However, major changes are unlikely, as spring locations are governed by hydrogeological dynamics operating on timescales far longer than the protohistoric period.

To adequately classify soils based on the reconstructed environment, the most suitable tool would be a pedological map. However, such maps are unavailable for much of the study area. To ensure consistent comparison across regions, we therefore relied on geological maps. These were analysed in conjunction with slope classes to identify landscape units, whose agricultural potential was grouped into six categories, ranging from Class 1 (most suitable) to Class 6 (unsuitable) (Fig 4, Appendix A). Landscape units and their classification are detailed in the Supplementary Information. The characteristics of each class are as follows:

- Class 1: Soils suitable for all agricultural uses; deep, fertile, easy to work, with good water availability. Typically suitable for cereals, legumes, or vineyards.
- Class 2: Soils with minor limitations, such as slightly reduced depth, mild stoniness, or moderate workability; only slightly less suitable than Class 1.
- Class 3: Soils with moderate limitations, including moderate depth, stoniness, slope, or groundwater influence. Generally suitable for tree crops (excluding vineyards), unless groundwater is the limiting factor; other crops are less viable.
- Class 4: Soils with significant limitations, such as shallow depth, high stoniness, or steep slopes. Best suited for grazing; tree crops may still be viable.
- Class 5: Soils with severe limitations, including very shallow depth, very high stoniness, or very steep slopes.
- Class 6: Soils unsuitable for any form of agriculture; may support woodland.

The area used to calculate the quantity and quality of available land corresponds to the zone within one hour of walking from the settlement centre, a threshold beyond which crop agriculture becomes less feasible (Bailey and Davidson, 1983; Vita-Finzi and Higgs, 1970). This distance (often expressed as a radius of 5 km) is commonly adopted in archaeology as the outer maximum limit of a settlement's agricultural catchment area (Bintliff, 2009, 2008; O'Connor and Evans, 2005; e.g. Pažout and Eisenberg, 2021; Rodriguez-Monterrubio, 2021). The amount of each soil class is expressed in square metres.

The complete dataset is in the supplementary S1 Table.

The Random Forest approach

To assess the influence of environmental variables on settlement location, we employed a Random Forest (RF) classification model. RF, an ensemble machine learning algorithm, constructs multiple decision trees and aggregates their predictions to improve accuracy and limit overfitting. Its robustness to multicollinearity,

capacity to capture complex non-linear relationships, and ability to quantify variable importance make it particularly well suited to archaeological data.

As with all binary classification algorithms, RF requires both positive and negative examples for training. In many archaeological contexts, the available data consist exclusively of known settlement locations, resulting in a presence-only dataset. To address this limitation, we generated pseudo-absence (or background) points: locations where settlement is assumed to be absent. The inclusion of these invented points is essential, as it transforms the problem from one of presence-only modelling to a presence-absence framework. This enables the use of standard predictive modelling techniques and allows the model to distinguish the characteristics of occupied versus unoccupied locations, thereby providing more robust and interpretable insights into the factors influencing settlement patterns (Hanberry et al., 2012; Senay et al., 2013). The pseudo-absence were generated randomly in QGIS, with a minimum distance of 500 meters from any known site (Wang et al., 2023). This constraint was introduced to minimize the likelihood that undocumented settlements might share similar values for the environmental parameters previously described in this section. However, it is important to stress that these points are not truly locations where no settlement exists, but rather places where no investigation has been carried out. As highlighted by Yaworsky et al. (Yaworsky et al., 2020), this violates the statistical assumptions underlying models such as RF and compromises the reliability of performance metrics, leading to an overestimation of the model's predictive capacity. However, it is important to emphasise that the objective of this study is not predictive modelling, but the exploratory assessment of variable importance. The inclusion of pseudo-absence points, while problematic in a strictly predictive framework due to the risk of incorporating undiscovered sites among the negative class, does not invalidate the present analysis. Here, pseudo-absences serve solely to provide a contrasting class, enabling the Random Forest algorithm to evaluate which variables most effectively discriminate between known settlements and background locations. Nevertheless, this approach may still affect the relative ranking of variables, especially if pseudo-absence points inadvertently share similar environmental properties with actual settlements. To mitigate this risk, we compared Random Forest outputs with independent statistical analyses (Alessandri, 2013). The results should therefore be understood not as predictions of settlement location, but as an exploratory identification of the environmental factors most strongly associated with settlement presence. The number of pseudo-absence points was selected following the recommendations of Barbet-Massin et al. (2012), who showed that for machine-learning classifiers such as Random Forests the most stable and accurate predictions are obtained when the number of pseudo-absences is of the same order of magnitude as the number of presences. Accordingly, we generated 100 pseudo-absence points for 110 known settlement locations (from Alessandri, 2013), resulting in a nearly balanced dataset, which is considered optimal for this class of models. The model was implemented using the free and open-source KNIME Analytics Platform (v. 5.5.0) (Fig 5). Below is a description of the workflow adopted for each chronological phase and for the dataset as a whole.

Preparing the dataset

The settlement and pseudo-absence point environmental parameters were initially used in their entirety and subsequently subdivided by chronological phases, considering only securely dated attributions. This supposedly allowed for the identification of phase-specific patterns. Before being fed into the model, the data were normalized using the Min–Max method.

Optimizing hyperparameters

Hyperparameters of the RF model (parameters that are not learned by the model itself but must be set prior to training), such as the number of trees (nrModels), maximum depth (maxLevels), and minimum number of samples per leaf (minNodeSize), were optimized through a grid search procedure combined with 10-fold cross-validation. In this approach, a predefined set of hyperparameter combinations is systematically tested (the grid search procedure), which involves exhaustively evaluating model performance across all specified

combinations of parameter values. Model performance is evaluated for each using repeated training and validation cycles (the cross-validation). During the cross-validation, the dataset is partitioned into ten equal subsets; in each iteration, nine subsets are used for training and one for validation, rotating through all folds. This procedure ensures that performance estimates are robust to variation in the training data and allows for the identification of the hyperparameter configuration that yields the best performance.

Model performance was evaluated using standard classification metrics (Flach, 2012): Recall (or Sensitivity), Precision, Specificity and F-measure score, as well as Accuracy and Cohen's Kappa, all calculated on the held-out test data. Recall measures the proportion of actual positive cases that are correctly identified, thus reflecting the model's ability to avoid false negatives. Precision quantifies the proportion of predicted positive cases that are true positives, indicating the model's ability to avoid false positives. Specificity measures the proportion of actual negative cases that are correctly identified, capturing the model's ability to avoid false positives and thus complementing recall. The F-measure score, calculated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall, offers a balanced measure of model performance, especially in cases where the classes are imbalanced. Accuracy measures the overall proportion of correct predictions. Cohen's Kappa (Cohen, 1960) indicates how much better the model's predictions are than random guessing, by correcting for agreement that could occur purely by chance. Following the guidelines proposed by Landis and Koch (1977), K values < 0.20 indicate poor agreement, 0.21–0.40 fair, 0.41–0.60 moderate, 0.61–0.80 substantial, and > 0.80 almost perfect agreement. In the context of settlement prediction, high recall reduces the risk of overlooking actual sites, while high precision minimizes the misclassification of non-sites as settlements.

For the purposes of this study, Recall on settlements was selected as the evaluation metric during the hyperparameter optimization phase. This choice, while reducing the model's precision by allowing a higher number of false positives, ensures that virtually all true settlements are captured. For the purposes of this study, which seeks to explore the relative importance of environmental factors rather than to predict settlement location, the trade-off is acceptable: minimising false negatives prevents the underestimation of variables that genuinely contributed to settlement siting, even if this comes at the cost of incorporating some noise into the analysis. The detailed parameters of each node are detailed in supplementary S2 Table.

Use of the best hyperparameters to train the Random Forest

A new Random Forest (RF) model was trained using the node parameters and hyperparameters obtained from the previous workflow, employing the same dataset. In the data partitioning process, 80% of the latter was assigned to the training set. Precision, Recall, Sensitivity, Specificity and F1 score, as well as Accuracy and Cohen's Kappa, were all calculated on the held-out test data.

Importances of environmental features

In the RF model, feature importance was quantified in two complementary ways. The first relies on the frequency with which each variable was used to split a node across all trees in the forest (split criterion, Gini index). These counts were then normalized, so that the importance value of each feature reflects its relative contribution to node partitioning within the ensemble. This approach highlights which variables most frequently contribute to dividing the data during model training, but it does not provide information on the direction of the association (i.e., whether a feature promotes or excludes settlement presence), nor does it necessarily correspond to true predictive influence. The second approach is based on SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), a cooperative game-theoretic framework that attributes to each feature its marginal contribution to a model's prediction, averaged over all possible coalitions of features (Lundberg and Lee, 2017; Shapley, 1952; Štrumbelj and Kononenko, 2014, 2011). Unlike split frequencies, SHAP values capture both the magnitude and the direction of a feature's effect on the output, thereby providing locally accurate and consistent explanations of individual predictions. For the global analysis (all phases combined), we

examined SHAP dependence values for each factor, restricted to real settlements and target class (Prediction) Yes (Prediction = Yes). In essence, the analysis is restricted to those cases in which the model correctly identified a settlement, with the aim of evaluating which factors exerted the strongest influence. At the level of individual phases, where the number of observations was too limited to produce reliable dependence plots, we instead employed the mean SHAP values for those factors, computed separately by phase and restricted to real settlements and the target class Yes (Prediction = Yes) as well.

Results

The ALL model, which aggregates all chronological phases, attains high predictive performance: Accuracy = 0.81; Kappa = 0.61 (S4 Table). Yet this model necessarily blends heterogeneous phase-specific patterns that do not correspond to a single territorial process. Statistically, its discriminant function represents an average response to environmental gradients drawn from distinct contexts. As a result, the model highlights those predictors that retain discriminative power across the full temporal sequence: even under internal heterogeneity, Random Forests tend to amplify variables that remain informative over large regions of the feature space. In this respect, the ALL model provides a robust indicator of the overall stability of each predictor in distinguishing sites from non-sites throughout the protohistoric period.

Although this model does not encode temporal information and cannot be used to infer phase-specific preferences, the chronological characterizations of points in the dependence plots offers a complementary descriptive perspective. It allows one to assess how different phases happen to be distributed across the environmental gradients captured by the model. These patterns do not reflect chronological effects learned by the algorithm, but they may nonetheless reveal whether particular phases cluster more frequently in regions where a variable exerts positive or negative influence. In this way, the ALL model helps differentiate predictors that show broadly consistent behaviour across time from those whose apparent effects arise from more context-dependent or spatially contingent configurations.

Using both the aggregated ALL model and the phase-specific models therefore enables a clear analytical distinction: the ALL model captures the intrinsic, temporally stable importance of predictors within the wider protohistoric landscape of Latium vetus, while the phase-resolved models illuminate the historical dynamics and shifting settlement strategies that unfolded within each individual period.

Global SHAP values, all phases combined

Here we will analyse the SHAP values referring only to those settlements whose existence was correctly predicted, without distinguishing them by phase (S5 Table). To analyse them more effectively, it is useful to examine the dependence plots (Fig 6, 7), where SHAP values are shown on the y-axis and the corresponding feature values on the x-axis. In this way, it becomes possible to observe how the predictive contribution changes (positively, >0 , or negatively, <0) as the value of the feature varies. A LOESS curve (frac = 0.5) (Cleveland and Devlin, 1988) has been added to each plot in order to estimate the overall trend.

This allows the directional contribution of predictors (whether monotonic, threshold-like or non-linear) to be identified, and highlights which variables retain robust predictive behaviour through time.

Altitude (Fig 6A) shows a clearly non-linear influence on settlement likelihood. A narrow band at very low elevation (0–25 m) contributes weakly but consistently positively, whereas most low altitudes (<200 m) exert a negative effect. A sharp positive peak emerges between 327 and 415 m, marking the most informative altitudinal interval for the model. At higher elevations, the effect remains positive but attenuates. This pattern indicates that altitude provides discriminative power only in specific segments of its range, with intermediate uplands contributing most strongly to site prediction. In this case, the positive value might be associated to

strategic visibility and defensibility. No clear altitude preferences emerge for individual phases, but it is interesting to note that among the sites clustering between 327 and 415 m, none are earlier than MBA3.

The dependence plot for **sea** (Fig 6B) exhibits a weak but structured non-linear effect, with a strong positive contribution at very short distances from the coast (<1 min.), a shallow negative trough at intermediate distances (6–80 min.), and a secondary positive signal around 342–514 min. This pattern suggests that the distance-to-coast variable captures two distinct environmental niches, immediate coastal settings and moderately inland positions, rather than a continuous gradient. The presence of Final Bronze Age sites within the closest distance band might indicate a phase-specific emphasis on coastal proximity.

The dependence plot for **water bodies** (Fig 6C) shows a relatively modest and short-range effect. At very short distances (<4 min.), SHAP values are frequently and strongly positive, indicating that immediate proximity to lakes and lagoons could enhance settlement probability. Such locations may have provided accessible water for domestic and agricultural use, as well as ecological advantages such as micro-environments suitable for exploitation. Beyond this narrow band, the predictor's influence collapses: most sites between 9 and 50 min. display near-zero or negative SHAP values, reflecting minimal discriminative power. At larger distances (>50 min.), SHAP values oscillate around zero (some positive, others negative) resulting in an overall mean close to zero and indicating the absence of a consistent directional effect at greater ranges. In summary, the plot suggests that water bodies acted as localised attractors, with positive effects only at immediate proximity. Once beyond that short range, their role in shaping settlement location quickly diminished and ultimately became negligible. The concentration of MBA3 sites within the high-SHAP cluster (5, 146, G49) further suggests that the strongest “water-adjacency” signal might be tied to specific phases of the protohistoric sequence rather than representing a uniform long-term pattern.

The dependence plot for **rivers** (Fig 6D) reveals a distinctly non-linear and internally heterogeneous relationship. Very short distances (<5 minutes) display the widest dispersion of SHAP values—ranging from markedly negative (down to -0.04) to clearly positive ($>+0.02$)—indicating that immediate river proximity encompasses multiple, context-dependent site types rather than a single behavioural signal. In the 5–20 min. range, the predictor's contribution is characterised by substantial variability. At greater distances (>20 minutes), SHAP values rise consistently, reaching up to ~ 0.03 , suggesting that far-from-river locations differentiate sites from pseudo-absences more reliably. This pattern, combined with the broad vertical scatter of observations, underscores that the influence of river proximity is not additive but strongly modulated by co-varying spatial and environmental factors outside the one-dimensional distance gradient.

The dependence plot for **springs** (Fig 6E) displays a sharply bipartite dependence structure. At very short distances (<9 min.), SHAP values are consistently positive, indicating that immediate proximity to springs exerted a favourable effect on site location. This pattern suggests that direct access to such reliable water sources was considered advantageous and may have been a decisive factor in settlement choice. However, after this walking distance, the curve enters a prolonged negative trough that extends until approximately 25 minutes. In this intermediate zone, SHAP values fall below zero, signalling that settlements located within this range contributed negatively to the model's predictions. A plausible interpretation is that springs were functionally valuable only if directly accessible: once the effort required to reach them exceeded a few minutes, their practical utility declined sharply. Consequently, sites situated within this “grey zone” appear less likely to have benefited from the presence of springs, which the model translates into a negative predictive contribution. Beyond around 30 minutes, the LOESS curve rises back towards zero and stabilises. At such distances, the presence or absence of springs no longer exerts a discernible influence on settlement location. The residual fluctuations visible in the curve are best interpreted as background noise, reflecting the influence of other variables rather than any meaningful effect of springs themselves. In summary, the plot suggests that springs were a highly localised factor of attraction: strongly positive when immediately

accessible, distinctly unfavourable at intermediate ranges where they were too far to be useful yet still within the landscape, and ultimately irrelevant beyond a certain threshold.

The dependence plot for **topographic settings** (Fig 6F) exhibits one of the strongest and most orderly dependence structures in the model. Plateau and ridge contexts yield the highest SHAP values, forming clear clusters of strongly positive contributions. Isolated peaks also show consistently positive effects, although less pronounced. In contrast, hills and plains display near-zero or negative SHAP values, and the single slope context yields a markedly negative contribution. Overall, the variable captures a robust hierarchical gradient in which elevated, stable, or topographically dominant settings are strongly associated with site presence, while low-lying or gently sloping terrains provide little or negative discriminative power.

Taken together, the SHAP dependence plots reveal that the geomorphological environmental predictors exert highly non-linear and predominantly short-range effects on settlement location, with contributions concentrated in narrow segments of each variable's domain rather than across continuous gradients.

The dependence plot for **C1** (Fig 7A) shows a structured but non-uniform pattern. At very low values of C1, SHAP contributions cluster around zero and span both slightly negative and slightly positive values, indicating that the near-absence of this highly fertile land class does not exert a strong or systematic influence on settlement likelihood. In this lower range (up to ~500 ha), C1 therefore appears to be only weakly informative, with no clear directional effect. Beyond this interval, however, SHAP values increasingly shift into positive territory. As the surface of C1 expands, the LOESS trend rises and the cloud of points becomes predominantly positive, suggesting that once a minimum extent is exceeded, larger areas of high-quality soils progressively enhance the probability of settlement. This points to a cumulative effect, whereby C1 begins to act as a robust positive predictor only after surpassing a threshold-like range rather than from its mere presence.

When the chronological information is considered, an additional layer of structure becomes visible. Sites belonging to the Bronze Age (EBA to FBA3) cluster almost entirely in the lower range of C1 values and display SHAP contributions close to or below zero. This indicates that highly fertile soils did not play a decisive role in the settlement strategies of the earlier communities. A gradual shift appears with the later RMCA phases, which dominate the upper segment of the C1 axis. Here, the positive effect of C1 becomes particularly pronounced, suggesting that during the later stages of the sequence the availability of extensive high-quality soils acquired a strong predictive power.

Nevertheless, a few notable exceptions emerge within the Middle and Recent Bronze Age. Two MBA3 sites (IDs 132 and 139) plot unusually high both in C1 extent (around 550 ha) and SHAP contribution, standing well above the main distribution for their period. Likewise, two further MBA sites (IDs 124 and 146) appear in the uppermost range of C1 (approaching 1000 ha) and also exhibit positive SHAP values. Although these cases do not alter the broader chronological trend, they might indicate that access to large tracts of fertile soils could occasionally influence settlement decisions even in earlier periods, highlighting some degree of variability within the MBA landscape.

Overall, the plot indicates that C1 did not operate as a simple presence/absence driver: limited patches alone were not sufficient to systematically favour settlement, whereas more substantial extents exerted a sustained and increasingly positive influence. The model thus captures a transition from a weak, near-neutral role at low values to a strong, monotonic positive contribution at higher surfaces.

By contrast, the interpretation of SHAP values for the other land classes is more ambiguous. **C2**, which is only slightly less fertile than C1, displays an apparently opposite behaviour (Fig 7B). At zero values, SHAP contributions are consistently and strongly positive, suggesting that even in the absence of C2 soils, settlement probability was enhanced. As the extent of C2 increases, however, the curve declines, becoming

negative just before c. 420 hectares. It then rises again towards positive values at around 4,000 hectares, although at such high magnitudes the pattern is likely distorted by interactions with other variables. This non-linear profile contrasts sharply with the steadily positive trend observed for C1 and underlines the complexity of interpreting SHAP values when multiple land classes are present.

The chronological distribution of the sites adds only a limited degree of structure to this pattern. Early and Middle Bronze Age settlements occur both in the highly positive low-C2 range and among the largest C2 values, suggesting that in these phases the presence of C2 could be advantageous under contrasting conditions. Beyond this, however, no clear or consistent chronological trend emerges. Overall, the chronological distribution does not align with a simple temporal gradient, indicating that the non-linear SHAP response of C2 is not primarily driven by chronology but rather by the spatial configuration of this soil class within the broader landscape.

The dependence plot for C3 displays a more stable pattern compared to C1 and C2 (Fig 7C). Small extents of this land class contribute positively to settlement probability, with several sites showing consistently high SHAP values in the lowest range of the distribution. Beyond approximately 600 ha, however, the curve declines sharply and enters distinctly negative territory around 900 ha, reaching its lowest values between c. 1,500 and 1,700 ha. At larger magnitudes the curve rises again, although SHAP contributions remain negative, indicating only a partial attenuation rather than a return to a positive influence. However, the non-linear and partly counterintuitive values observed beyond around 900 hectares should not be interpreted as a genuine disadvantage. Rather, they indicate that once the available surface exceeded the scale of land actually exploitable by a community, additional hectares became irrelevant for settlement choice. In practical terms, the difference between 1 and 10 hectares of workable soil could have been decisive, but the difference between 1,000 and 2,000 hectares was likely of no consequence, as only a fraction of that land would have been directly utilised. At such magnitudes, SHAP values no longer capture the intrinsic role of the variable but instead reflect background noise and interactions with other factors. Chronology does not appear to structure this pattern: sites of different phases are dispersed across positive, negative, and intermediate values, suggesting that the behaviour of C3 is not temporally driven but instead reflects local landscape configurations and the relative distribution of this land class within each catchment. Overall, these results highlight a pattern of diminishing returns, whereby fertile soils were crucial up to a certain threshold (which may be around 900 ha), but beyond that point their contribution plateaued and ultimately became negligible.

The contribution of C4 is negligible, as it is distributed in only minimal quantities within the study area (Fig 7D).

C5 (Fig 7E) exhibits a generally weak signal, with one minor but notable exception: for very small extents (up to approximately 144 ha), SHAP values are consistently positive, indicating that limited patches of this land class may have contributed to increasing settlement probability. This effect, however, dissipates rapidly. Beyond this threshold, C5 yields predominantly negative or near-zero SHAP values, and this subdued pattern persists across most of its distribution. Unlike C1, C2 and C3, C5 does not display extended intervals of positive influence, nor does it reveal any coherent chronological pattern. Overall, C5 emerges as a land class with low predictive power: beneficial only when present in very small quantities and quickly becoming irrelevant, or mildly disadvantageous.

For C6 (Fig 7F), it is important to note first that the scale of the surfaces involved is very limited, representing only minimal portions of the landscape. Within this narrow range, the dependence plot reveals a modest positive signal at very small extents, restricted to just a few tens of hectares, followed by a rapid decline towards values oscillating around zero. The amplitude of these fluctuations remains consistently low, indicating that C6 exerts only a marginal influence on the model's predictions. No coherent chronological trend can be identified, as sites of different phases are scattered throughout the full range of values. In other

words, the variable displays limited predictive power, with no clear trend strong enough to significantly affect settlement likelihood.

Taken together, the soil dependence plots do not point to a uniform behaviour of the most fertile land classes, but rather reveal a differentiated set of responses. C1 emerges as a threshold-driven predictor, exerting little influence at low values but becoming a strong and steadily positive driver only once its extent exceeds a minimum range. C2, despite being only slightly less fertile, displays a markedly non-linear and partly counterintuitive pattern, with positive contributions at both very low and very high values and a negative interval in between, suggesting that its effect is strongly contingent on local configurations and interactions with other variables rather than on its absolute availability. By contrast, C3 shows the most coherent behaviour among the fertile classes, with positive contributions at small to moderate extents and a pattern of diminishing returns beyond the scale likely to have been practically exploitable by communities.

The less fertile classes, C5 and C6, in turn, exhibit weak and inconsistent signals, with only minor positive effects restricted to very small surfaces and predominantly neutral or negative contributions elsewhere, indicating a marginal role in shaping settlement choices. Overall, rather than defining a simple fertility gradient, the dependence plots highlight that different soil classes contributed to settlement location through distinct mechanisms: threshold-like responses (C1), context-dependent and non-linear effects (C2), and cumulative but saturating influences (C3), while poorer soils played only a secondary or negligible role.

Normalized split frequencies

Normalized split frequencies show a clear shift in the predictors used by the model to discriminate archaeological sites from non-sites across the chronological sequence (Figs. 8-10). In the earliest phases (EBA–MBA12), hydrological variables dominate: Rivers reaches very high values (1.00 and 0.61), and both Springs and Water bodies exhibit strong contributions (up to 1.00 and 0.71), whereas topographic setting remains negligible (0.02–0.10). From MBA3 onwards, topographic structure becomes increasingly informative, with topographic setting rising sharply (0.65 in FBA12) and attaining maximum importance in all phases from FBA3 to RMCAIII (1.00). Altitude contributes consistently across the entire sequence (0.52–0.98), peaking in FBA12.

Proximity to the coast (Sea) displays moderate values in earlier periods (0.36–0.50) but intensifies from RBA onward, reaching 0.79 in both RBA and FBA12 and remaining high in RMCA phases (0.59–0.75). Hydrological predictors retain variable but non-negligible influence in later phases, including a marked increase in Springs in RMCAIII (0.91).

Soil-fertility classes (C1–C6) show heterogeneous contributions (Fig 10), with C1 and C2 maintaining moderate values across phases, while C6 becomes highly informative in specific intervals (1.00 in MBA3 and FBA12). C4 remains generally low across the sequence.

Together, these patterns document a progressive reweighting of the predictors used by the model, from an early emphasis on hydrological availability to a sustained dominance of topographic factors in later periods.

Phase-by-phase mean SHAP values

Here we will analyse, phase by phase, the mean SHAP values for each feature (Fig 11). The values refer only to those settlements whose existence was correctly predicted (S6 Table).

It must be emphasised that the number of sites from which reliable inferences can be drawn is extremely limited, in some cases fewer than five for the earliest phases. From the Iron Age onwards (RMCA IIA), the

situation improves owing to the larger number of attestations, yet the overall sample remains very restricted which means that the patterns identified here should be regarded as exploratory signals rather than confirmatory evidence. The results are best interpreted as heuristic insights pointing to recurrent trends that require further testing, rather than as statistically robust demonstrations of settlement behaviour.

Across the chronological sequence, the mean SHAP values reveal a progressive reconfiguration of the environmental factors that contribute to distinguishing archaeological sites from non-sites (Figs 12, 13). In the earliest phases (EBA and MBA12), the model draws predominantly on hydrological variables, with springs providing the most substantive contribution. During these phases, the influence of topographic setting remains minimal and altitude plays only a marginal role, while soil-fertility classes (C1-2) form a dominant signal only in EBA. This pattern suggests that, in the earliest periods captured by the model, local hydrological availability and soil fertility constitute the most informative dimension for separating sites from their surrounding landscapes. A gradual but clear transition begins in MBA3, where topographic setting starts to exert a measurable effect for the first time, accompanied by a residual but still relevant contribution of springs. This marks the onset of a shift away from hydrological dependence, although the overall distribution of predictive weight remains relatively diffuse. In the subsequent RBA phase, the contributions of individual variables remain generally low and dispersed, and no single predictor clearly dominates the discrimination process; the model operates here through a weaker and more evenly distributed signal. From FBA12 onward, however, the structure of model importance changes decisively. Topographic setting becomes the most informative variable by a substantial margin, and its contribution continues to intensify in FBA3 and both RMCA phases, where it consistently emerges as the dominant predictor. In these later phases, altitude provides a modest but stable secondary contribution, while hydrological variables decline sharply, retaining only episodic or negligible importance. Soil-fertility classes remain low and inconsistent across all phases, never forming a coherent temporal pattern and contributing only weakly to the model's predictive performance.

Taken together, the phase-specific mean SHAP values confirm and refine the trends already highlighted by the normalized split frequencies, by identifying which predictors not only structure the model but also actively favour site occurrence. While the earliest phases are characterised by positive contributions from hydrological availability (and, locally, soil fertility), from FBA12 onward topographic setting emerges as the only factor exerting a strong and persistent positive influence on site presence, with altitude providing a secondary reinforcement. In contrast, hydrological and pedological variables progressively lose any systematic positive effect, indicating that in the later phases they no longer attract settlement but instead operate mainly as contextual or exclusionary conditions within an increasingly canalised settlement logic.

Discussion

Comparison with the statistical framework

The only study on Latium Vetus that applies a statistical test (one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov goodness-of-fit test, two-tailed) to settlement distribution for these periods is Alessandri 2013, which thus provides the most appropriate framework within which to contextualise the Random Forest results. That study demonstrated that access to freshwater springs was a statistically significant determinant of settlement location throughout the protohistoric sequence of Latium Vetus (and plausibly beyond). Specifically, the clustering of settlements within 12.2 minutes of a spring was found to be significant. This threshold is very close to the 9-minute break point identified by the LOESS approximation of SHAP values, at which the predictive contribution of springs shifts from positive to negative. That proximity to springs, and to potable water sources more broadly, served as a major driver, particularly in the earliest phases, is also supported by both the split-frequency analysis and the phase-resolved SHAP values. This concordance reinforces the

interpretation of an interval around 10 minutes from water sources as a critical threshold for settlement siting.

Alessandri 2013 also identified proximity to the sea and altitude as statistically significant variables. In the case of the sea, a clustering of settlements within 62.7 minutes was observed, closely matching the 54.1-minute threshold in the SHAP dependence plot where the LOESS curve crosses from positive to negative.

For altitude, the statistical analysis identified two significant clusters, below 33 m and between 281–381 m, while the SHAP-based LOESS curve indicates positive values below 25 m and from 237 m upwards. The correspondence is again substantial, with the exception of the upper range, where the SHAP curve relies on only two settlements. The split frequencies likewise indicate that elevation contributes a consistent amount of information across all phases. As previously observed, the SHAP values and split frequencies in this case may be interpreted as reflecting the onset of conflict from the close of the Middle Bronze Age onwards, a development that appears to have favoured the selection of more defensible locations. The agreement between the SHAP-derived thresholds and those obtained through classical statistical tests is therefore notable. These parallels should not be viewed as formal validation, yet they amount to more than incidental correspondence. The recurrence of similar breakpoints across independent analytical frameworks indicates a coherent signal that plausibly reflects underlying settlement-selection processes. Although additional analyses on expanded datasets will be required to test the generality of these thresholds, the present convergence of results already provides a robust, multi-method basis for their interpretation.

Interpretation of the results from a (proto)historic perspective

Taken together, all these observations point to a systematic, long-term shift in the dimensions along which settlement location differs from non-settlement areas (all metrics in S4 table).

EBA and MBA12 (2100-1400 BCE): dispersed settlement driven by hydrological features.

Both the normalized split frequencies and the mean SHAP values for the earliest phases (EBA and MBA12) (Fig 14, 15) indicate, on the one hand, that the site's morphological characteristics have a negligible impact, and on the other, that the model relies primarily on hydrological predictors, reflecting a landscape in which access to water is the most informative feature distinguishing sites from their surroundings. Access to rivers and water bodies, beyond providing potable water, may also have reflected the need to settle along major and easily navigable communication corridors, valleys often serving as preferential movement routes, or the opportunity to exploit specific ecological niches such as freshwater fishing or the hunting of migratory waterfowl. An illustrative case of the latter is the site of Villaggio delle Macine (EBA-MBA1/2), where archaeozoological analyses indicate a strong incidence of hunting activity, with the presence of deer and roe deer, together with ichthyofauna and turtles (Angle and Guidi, 2007). It is worth also noting A. Guidi's hypothesis suggesting that settlement proximity to perennial water sources may have been influenced by a particularly arid climatic phase, as evidenced by palynological analyses from the surrounding regions (Guidi, 2003).

As previously noted, the MBA12 also appears to mark an expansive phase in which multiple territorial domains were being actively explored. Technically, this is reflected in a model with only moderate discriminative power: although Sensitivity/Recall is relatively high (0.75, the model correctly identifies 75% of the MBA12 sites), Precision remains limited (0.60, only 60% of the points that the model predicts as MBA12 sites are actually MBA12 sites.), suggesting that the environmental conditions characterizing MBA12 sites are not yet sufficiently distinctive to separate them cleanly from the surrounding landscape. In this context, the weak differentiation between sites and non-sites forces the model to operate with relatively broad criteria to intercept the majority of true sites, at the cost of an increased incidence of false positives.

The low Cohen's kappa (0.25) underscores the weak and only partially structured landscape signal. Finally, with respect to soils, soil class C2, characterized by high fertility and suitability for all crops, emerges as the most significant predictor in the EBA phase based on normalized split frequencies and mean SHAP values, whereas in the subsequent phase soil quality appears to exert minimal explanatory power.

MBA3 (1400-1300 BCE): the beginning of a structured landscape

From a technical standpoint, the transition to MBA3 (Fig 16) marks a clear shift in regime: the model's discriminatory power increases substantially, and the landscape signal becomes far more structured. For the "site" class (Yes), Precision reaches 1.00, indicating a complete absence of false positives (every location predicted as an MBA3 site is indeed a true site). Sensitivity/Recall (0.67) remains moderate, showing that not all sites are detected, but those that are detected are classified with perfect reliability. Specificity for this class (1.00) further demonstrates that the decision boundary between sites and non-sites is sharply defined, with no unoccupied areas misclassified as settlements.

These changes are mirrored in the overall performance: Accuracy rises to 0.83, and, crucially, Cohen's kappa increases to 0.67, shifting from only slight agreement beyond chance in the MBA12 (0.25) to substantial agreement. Technically, this indicates that the overlap between the environmental "signatures" of sites and non-sites diminishes dramatically: the model no longer needs to rely on broad and inclusive criteria but can instead adopt a much more selective decision rule, reducing noise and virtually eliminating false positives. In strictly metric terms, the pattern reveals an evolution from a model that is "sensitive but weakly selective" (MBA12: high Sensitivity/Recall, moderate Precision, low Kappa) to one that is "more selective and better calibrated" (MBA3: perfect Precision, perfect Specificity, substantially higher Kappa), reflecting settlement choices that are more focused, more coherent, and statistically more separable from the surrounding landscape.

The mean SHAP values indicate that, for the first time, topographic setting emerges as the primary driver in settlement location choice. This pattern is less evident in the normalized split frequencies; however, the substantial increase in their significance is still notable (from 0.10 in the MBA12 to 0.44). This phase is indeed characterized by a numerical rise in settlements located in defensible and moderately defensible positions. Equally noteworthy is the territorial distribution of defensible settlements (Fig 17). In the Colli Albani, they appear to be positioned at three vertices of an imaginary square, and whose territories, reconstructed through the Bubble Model (Alessandri, 2016a), are practically all tangent to one another at a distance slightly less than a 60-minute walk. Along the coast, defensible settlements are distributed at intervals of approximately 4 hours' walking distance (Ficana to Pratica di Mare, 235 min.; Pratica di Mare to Colle Rotondo, 259 min.). Furthermore, five of the settlements in defensible or moderate defensible positions persist into the subsequent phase: Ficana (L1D), Pratica di Mare (L4A), Colle dei Cappuccini (3), Rome (F19/F22), and Colle della Mola (4); the first four continue well into the Iron Age.

RBA (1300-1150 BCE): the emerging of social complexity

As observed in the MBA12, where exploratory dynamics forced the model to rely on broad decision criteria, the RBA phase (Fig 18) again exhibits a marked weakening of the landscape signal and a reduced capacity to discriminate effectively between sites and non-sites. From a technical perspective, performance for the "site" class drops sharply: Sensitivity/Recall falls to 0.33, indicating that only one-third of RBA sites are correctly identified, while Precision (0.50) shows that half of the predicted sites are in fact false positives. Although Specificity remains relatively high (0.86), suggesting that non-sites are generally well recognised, the model struggles to delineate what constitutes a true RBA site.

Indeed, overall performance metrics (Accuracy = 0.70; Cohen's kappa = 0.21) indicate only weak agreement beyond chance, positioning the RBA closer to the loosely structured signal of MBA12. Technically, this

suggests that environmental signatures characteristic of RBA sites are again widely shared across the landscape, preventing the model from establishing a stable and selective decision boundary. In contrast to the clear and focused environmental preferences emerging in the MBA3, the RBA reflects a phase in which settlement patterns are less coherent from a predictive standpoint, producing a statistically diffuse signal that constrains the model's ability to achieve robust discrimination.

Further underscoring the internally inconsistent character of this phase, the normalized split frequencies and mean SHAP values yield divergent signals. The former continue the long-standing trend from the EBA, identifying hydrological variables as the principal drivers of settlement location, whereas the latter assign these same parameters a negative association with site presence. A comparable inversion emerges for the topographic setting: SHAP values indicate a favourable effect, while the split frequencies suggest that its contribution is minimal.

The apparent inconsistency between normalized split frequencies and mean SHAP values in this phase reflects the fact that the two indicators quantify different properties of the model. Split frequencies quantify how often a variable reduces impurity in the tree structure, irrespective of the direction of its effect. A feature may therefore be highly informative for identifying non-sites, leading to frequent splits, without contributing positively to the prediction of sites. In contrast, mean SHAP values encode the signed contribution of a predictor to the target class: a variable that consistently pushes predictions toward the "non-site" class will exhibit negative SHAP values, even if it is structurally important for the model. In such cases, the SHAP ranking appears reversed not because the feature is uninformative, but because its discriminative power acts primarily against the presence of a site.

In the Colli Albani, the occupation of Maschio dei Ferrari completes the settlement framework anticipated in the previous phase, effectively saturating the Vulcano Laziale. Along the coast, newly founded defensible sites such as Ardea and Monte di Leva fill the gaps left open earlier, and their presence appears to structure surrounding settlement patterns: within their spheres of influence, smaller non-defensible sites sometimes tend to cluster, suggesting forms of hierarchical or gravitational organization (Fig 19). A notable exception is the cluster east of Rome, where no settlement emerges as a clear focal point. In the immediate vicinity of Colle Rotondo, the earliest cremation cemetery of Latium Vetus, Cavallo Morto, marks a striking shift in funerary practice, replacing earlier cave inhumations that, as far as we know, were accessible to the entire community. The small size of these cemeteries, here and in the ensuing Final Bronze Age, implies a more restricted access to burial, pointing to emerging social differentiation. At the same time, the first appearances of Mycenaean and Italo-Mycenaean pottery at Rome (Baroni and Copat, 2019) and at Casale Nuovo to the south signal the integration of the region into long-distance exchange networks that transmitted not only goods but also ideas and technical expertise. Overall, the Recent Bronze Age stands out as a rapidly evolving phase in which multiple innovations converge, reflecting profound shifts in socio-economic structures and marking the onset of trajectories that will become clearer in the following periods and will culminate on the eve of the Iron Age.

FBA12 (1150-1050 BCE): territorial stabilisation

The FBA12 phase (Fig 20) displays an exceptionally clear and internally coherent settlement signal, yielding a model performance that is mathematically perfect across all metrics. For both the "site" and "non-site" classes, Recall, Precision, Sensitivity, Specificity, and F-measure all reach 1.00, indicating that the classifier distinguishes flawlessly between occupied and unoccupied areas. No false positives or false negatives are produced: every FBA12 site is correctly identified, and every non-site is accurately excluded. The resulting Accuracy of 1.00 and Cohen's kappa of 1.00 attest to complete agreement beyond chance, a level unattainable in phases characterised by ambiguous or weak ecological signatures. Such a result strongly suggests that, by FBA12, settlement choices have become highly canalised, reflecting a consolidated socio-ecological configuration in which site locations align with very specific environmental settings. The sharp

statistical separability is therefore not an artefact of modelling, but a genuine reflection of a landscape in which communities operated according to well-defined and stable criteria.

The mean SHAP values indicate that, from this point onward and through to the RMCA III phase, the settlement pattern is driven primarily by topographic setting. The normalized split frequencies once again appear inverted; however, as in the preceding phase, this reflects the different aspects captured by the two metrics rather than a substantive inconsistency. SHAP values also reveal a significant contribution of elevation, likely linked to a preference for raised locations. This is clearly expressed by the SHAP values aggregated for topographic setting, which consistently assign positive effects to isolated peaks, plateaus, and ridges, and by those for elevation, which show a predominantly positive influence within the 327–415 m range.

At the territorial scale, the spatial configuration of sites, particularly the group of smaller settlements forming a ring around the Roman core at around 130 minutes from the Capitoline/Palatine system, suggests that the effective radius of control exercised by major, defensible centres may have nearly doubled (Fig 21). When the same radius is applied to the larger coastal settlements, their spheres of influence tend to be mutually tangent, with the notable exception of the boundary between Ardea and Pratica di Mare, whereas in the remaining areas a limit of approximately one hour's walking distance appears to persist. Several additional necropoleis have been identified in the region, all consisting of few and isolated cremation burials, broadly comparable in conception to those of the RBA. Overall, the FBA12 phase appears to stand in direct continuity with the preceding period, without marked discontinuities, while consolidating the settlement logic that emerges at the end of the Bronze Age.

FBA3 (1050-950 BCE): institutionalisation of inequality

The FBA3 phase maintains a very high level of model performance, confirming the consolidation of a strongly structured settlement signal already evident in FBA12, while reintroducing a limited degree of variability (Fig 22). For the “site” class, the model achieves a Precision of 1.00, indicating the complete absence of false positives: every location classified as an FBA3 site corresponds to a true settlement. Sensitivity/Recall (0.75) remains high, showing that most sites are correctly identified, although a small number of false negatives persist. The corresponding F-measure (0.86) reflects a well-balanced trade-off between Sensitivity and selectivity. For the “non-site” class, performance is similarly robust, with Sensitivity/Recall = 1.00 and Precision = 0.80, indicating that all non-sites are correctly recognised, albeit with a minor degree of confusion when distinguishing them from true sites. At the aggregate level, Accuracy reaches 0.87 and Cohen's kappa increases to 0.75, signalling substantial agreement beyond chance and confirming the persistence of a sharply defined settlement logic.

From a modelling perspective, these metrics indicate that the environmental and topographic signatures governing site location in FBA3 remain highly discriminative, though slightly less rigid than in the perfectly separable FBA12. The limited re-emergence of false negatives suggests not a weakening of the overall signal, but rather a modest broadening of the decision space within an otherwise stable and well-canalised settlement system. In continuity with the previous phase, settlement choices in FBA3 appear strongly constrained by specific landscape configurations, allowing the model to operate with narrow decision boundaries and high confidence while accommodating minor local variability.

This time, both the mean SHAP values and the normalized split frequencies consistently identify the topographic setting as by far the most important driver in the selection (or long-term maintenance) of settlement location.

The FBA3 phase marks the first clear appearance of the so-called Rome–Colli Albani ceramic facies (subphase I). This facies is defined primarily through funerary material culture: burial practices continue to

be characterised by cremation, reserved for restricted segments of the population and accompanied by highly standardised assemblages. Within this framework, however, several important innovations emerge. Most striking is the sharp increase in the number of necropoleis and isolated graves, which rises from only three attestations in FBA12 to thirty-six in FBA3, indicating the rapid regional diffusion of the rite and, by extension, of the value system underpinning it. This expansion is further reflected in the spatial distribution of funerary evidence, which now covers almost the entirety of the Latium Vetus, with the southernmost occurrence extending even beyond the study area, at Bosco del Polverino.

Two features of the grave goods are particularly revealing. The first is the widespread miniaturisation of selected ceramic and metal objects, including razors, lances, swords, greaves and double shields (Alessandri, 2013; De Santis, 2011). Although the precise meaning of this practice remains elusive, it closely parallels the prominent role of miniature vessels in ritual contexts, especially in chthonic cults and in votive deposits associated with water bodies. In our area, a well-known example is the Laghetto del Monsignore at Campoverde, where thousands of miniature vessels, together with high-value artefacts in full size, were deposited over a long chronological span, from RMCA IIA, with possible earlier elements in FBA3, through to the fifth century BCE (Van Loon, 2017). The second salient feature is the exceptional wealth of many funerary assemblages, exemplified by the necropolis of Santa Palomba, where miniature bronze chariots frequently accompany the cremation urns (De Santis, 2021). Notably, such rich assemblages are often associated with juvenile individuals, as in tomb 5 at Le Caprine, where a child of approximately two years of age was buried with an exceptionally elaborate set of grave goods (Damiani et al., 1998).

Taken together, the selective adoption of the cremation rite, the richness and standardisation of the assemblages, their association with individuals of all ages, and the pervasive role of miniaturisation in both funerary and votive contexts point to the emergence of a dominant elite whose status was inherited at birth, marking the institutionalization of inequality. Funerary ritual appears to have functioned as a key medium for the public expression and reproduction of this status, and possibly for the post-mortem elevation of the deceased to a semi-divine or ancestral sphere.

The existence of elites plausibly rooted in kinship-based groups accords well with the simultaneous emergence of incipient hierarchical differentiation among defensible settlements within the same territories, a locational parameter that from this point onward strongly shapes settlement choices (Fig 23). Such sites likely functioned as the seats of these elites, alongside other settlements that may have fulfilled roles extending beyond purely residential functions. Further, as previously suggested by R. Peroni (Peroni, 1996), in socio-economic systems where land ownership remained largely communal, elite economic strategies were necessarily directed toward alternative domains; among these, salt production appears particularly significant. In the Latium Vetus, the earliest evidence for this activity dates to the FBA12 phase, at the site of Pelliccione (Nijboer et al., 2006), where salt was most likely produced using briquetage techniques.

RMCA IIA (950-880 BCE): elite expansion

The RMCA IIA phase maintains a high level of model performance, while marking a subtle shift away from the near-perfect rigidity observed in the terminal phases of the Bronze Age (Fig 24). For the “site” class, the model achieves perfect Precision (1.00), indicating the complete absence of false positives: all locations classified as settlements correspond to true sites. Sensitivity/Recall (0.71) is moderately lower, reflecting the presence of a limited number of false negatives and suggesting that some settlements fall outside the most restrictive decision boundary. The resulting F-measure (0.83) confirms a strong but no longer optimal balance between sensitivity and selectivity. At the aggregate level, Accuracy reaches 0.80 and Cohen’s kappa equals 0.60, signalling substantial agreement beyond chance, albeit lower than in FBA3. Together,

these metrics indicate a settlement logic that remains highly selective and well structured, yet slightly more permissive than in the immediately preceding phases.

This pattern is closely mirrored by the feature-importance metrics. Both the mean SHAP values and the normalized split frequencies converge in identifying topographic setting as the dominant driver of settlement location. The mean SHAP value for topographic setting is by far the highest among all predictors (0.135), indicating a strong and consistently positive contribution to site prediction. At the same time, its normalized split frequency reaches the maximum possible value (1.0), demonstrating that this variable is systematically selected during tree construction to reduce impurity. Unlike earlier phases characterised by divergences between the two metrics, here structural importance and predictive contribution are fully aligned, pointing to a mature and internally coherent settlement logic in which topographic configuration functions as both a primary filter and a decisive attractor.

Secondary variables play a clearly subordinate role. Altitude retains a modest but positive SHAP contribution, consistent with its close coupling to topographic preferences rather than acting as an independent driver. Hydrological variables (rivers, springs, water bodies, and sea) exhibit near-zero or slightly negative SHAP values, despite relatively high split frequencies, particularly for rivers and the sea. This combination indicates that these parameters remain useful for structuring decision boundaries within the forest, but contribute little, or even marginally negatively, to the final prediction of sites. Their role is therefore best interpreted as contextual or exclusionary, rather than as direct drivers of settlement choice.

Taken together, the convergence of performance and importance metrics suggests that RMCA IIA represents a phase of consolidated selectivity. Settlement choices are anchored to a narrowly defined set of landscape configurations, dominated by topographic setting, allowing the model to operate with high confidence and minimal commission error (Fig 25). At the same time, the moderate reduction in recall signals a limited broadening of the occupied niche, consistent with a controlled diversification within an otherwise stable and canalised settlement system. Rather than indicating a breakdown of the spatial logic established in the Late Bronze Age, RMCA IIA appears to reflect a phase of measured adjustment and reorganisation at the threshold of the Early Iron Age. More specifically, the coastal sectors, the areas close to the Tiber, and the northern portion of the Colli Albani remain largely stable. By contrast, the variability detected by the model is concentrated in the southern Colli Albani, where a process of territorial reorganisation, still operating within the settlement logics identified thus far, leads to the emergence of Lanuvio, Cisterna and Satricum, proto-urban centres that would persist well beyond the Iron Age.

From a socio-economic perspective, this pattern is best understood as the spatial consolidation of processes already observed in the preceding phase. The incipient hierarchisation among defensible settlements identified for the FBA3 becomes fully operational in the RMCA IIA, as elevated and morphologically distinctive locations function as stable territorial anchors through which elite power was exercised, rendered visible, and reproduced. The slightly reduced recall observed in this phase does not signal a relaxation of the underlying drivers, but rather the emergence of a more articulated settlement system. While the core locational logic remains highly selective and tightly anchored to topographic setting, resulting in perfect precision and the absence of false positives, a limited number of sites fall outside this dominant pattern, likely reflecting functional differentiation within an increasingly hierarchical territorial organisation. Settlement placement thus becomes a normative act embedded within a structured political economy, in which social regulation increasingly outweighs environmental opportunity alone.

A further indication of the expansive dynamics characterising this phase is offered by the necropoleis. During the RMCA IIA phase, Rome witnesses a systematic relocation of funerary areas away from the urban core, likely driven by the spatial demands of an expanding settlement. Burial grounds are first displaced from the area of the Arch of Augustus to that of the Temple of Antoninus and Faustina in RMCA IIA, and

subsequently, during RMCA IIA2 or at the latest at the onset of RMCA IIB, moved further to the Esquiline Hill. A comparable reconfiguration can be inferred for the Capitoline necropoleis, which shift from the Forum of Caesar to the Forum of Augustus, and later, in RMCA IIB, to the Quirinal Hill (Alessandri, 2013; Guidi, 2024).

Similar dynamics are evident beyond Rome. At Pratica di Mare, the necropolis located on the main plateau is confined to the Final Bronze Age, while in RMCA IIA burials are relocated just outside it, suggesting that the plateau itself had by then become an inhabited area (Jaia, 2007). An analogous process has been proposed for Ardea, where the plateau of Civitavecchia appears to have been occupied at the beginning of the Iron Age, and possibly already from the Final Bronze Age (Modica, 2011).

The funerary record also provides further insights into the organisation and internal structuring of society which once again displays substantial innovations. Most notably, this phase marks a decisive shift from cremation to inhumation as the dominant burial rite. While cremation does not disappear entirely, it becomes increasingly restricted and appears to be reserved for the most eminent individuals, suggesting a growing differentiation in access to ritual practices. Inhumation, by contrast, becomes the normative mode of burial, signalling a redefinition of funerary behaviour at the level of the broader community. This transformation is not merely ritual but social in nature, as it reflects changing mechanisms of identity construction and social reproduction.

At the same time, the internal organisation of necropoleis provides further clues to the structuring of social groups. The spatial arrangement of burials at Osteria dell'Osa (Bietti Sestieri, 1992), in particular, is characterised by the clustering of graves into distinct groups, a pattern that plausibly reflects segmentation along kinship lines. Rather than representing a homogeneous burial ground, the necropolis appears organised into discrete family units, each maintaining its own funerary space across generations. Within this framework, the selective persistence of cremation for high-status individuals can be interpreted as a strategy of distinction adopted by dominant lineages, reinforcing their social pre-eminence through the maintenance of an exceptional ritual practice. Together, the coexistence of different rites and the spatial segmentation of burial grounds point to a society in which inequality was no longer merely expressed through wealth or display but structurally embedded in both ritual norms and genealogical organisation.

RMCA IIB (880-800 BCE): persistence of topographic control

The RMCA IIB phase (Fig 26) confirms the persistence of a highly structured and selective settlement system. For the “site” class, the model again attains perfect Precision (1.00), indicating the complete absence of false positives and thus a very conservative decision boundary: every predicted site corresponds to a true settlement. Sensitivity/Recall remains at 0.71, with a small number of false negatives, yielding an F-measure of 0.83. This asymmetric configuration mirrors that observed in RMCA IIA and implies a system in which the core locational logic is tightly constrained, while a limited subset of sites falls outside the dominant pattern.

This behaviour is closely reflected in the feature-importance metrics. Both mean SHAP values and normalized split frequencies converge in identifying topographic setting as the principal driver of settlement location. Its mean SHAP contribution (0.090) is by far the highest among all predictors, and its split frequency reaches the maximum value (1.0), indicating that it is systematically used to structure the forest and exerts a strong positive influence on site prediction. As in RMCA IIA, topographic configuration thus acts simultaneously as a structural filter and a decisive attractor, confirming the centrality of elevated and morphologically distinctive locations in shaping the occupied niche.

Secondary predictors display a markedly subordinate and more ambiguous role. Altitude retains a modest positive SHAP contribution (0.019), consistent with its close coupling to topographic preferences rather than an independent driving role. Hydrological variables (rivers, springs, sea, water bodies) show moderate to high split frequencies, particularly for the sea (0.59) and springs (0.57), but near-zero or even negative SHAP values, indicating that while they remain useful for partitioning the feature space, they contribute little, or marginally negatively, to the final prediction of sites. Their role is therefore best interpreted as contextual or exclusionary, helping to define where sites are unlikely to occur rather than actively attracting settlement.

The convergence of performance and importance metrics indicates that RMCA IIB represents a phase of continuity and stabilisation within the structured settlement logic established in the Late Bronze Age and consolidated in RMCA IIA. The persistence of perfect precision, coupled with slightly reduced recall, suggests that the core locational rules anchored in topographic setting remain firmly in place, while a limited number of sites reflect a controlled diversification within an increasingly articulated territorial system.

At this stage, the territory itself was likely approaching, if not already reaching, full saturation. Most ecologically and strategically viable locations had been occupied, leaving little room for further expansion without disrupting the existing balance. This condition of spatial closure also provides a powerful explanation for the crystallisation of settlement patterns detected by the model.

At the territorial scale (Fig 27), the continuity of major centres and the limited diversification of secondary sites point to a political economy oriented toward the management of already integrated territories rather than their expansion. Most of the areas occupied by the major centres show evidence of spatial expansion. This is the case, as already noted, for Rome, which probably began to expand as early as RMCA IIA, but also for Pratica di Mare and Ardea, whose settlements extend onto the adjacent plateaus. In this phase, it is also possible to discern with some clarity an important territorial differentiation. If one considers the size of the settlements (where this can be estimated), two distinct organisational patterns seem to emerge. In the first, larger and dominant centres share the territory with much smaller, and plausibly subordinate, sites. This appears to be the case, for example, for Rome with Acqua Acetosa (and perhaps Antemnae), Ardea with l'Altare, and possibly Pratica di Mare with Tredici Altari. In the second pattern, by contrast, centres of comparable size coexist, as in the systems formed by Ficana and Castel di Decima; Tusculum with Colonna and Prato della Corte; Colle dei Cappuccini with Ariccia and Monte Cavo; and Anzio with Colle Rotondo. This evidence suggests the coexistence of a territorially organised system based on hierarchy, on the one hand, and a more federative arrangement, on the other, the latter being characteristic of the Alban Hills area. Although such federative systems are notoriously difficult to identify in the protohistoric archaeological record, they find echoes in later sources, such as the league of the Populi Albenses, which comprised thirty communities gravitating around the Colli Albani (Fulminante, 2014; Grandazzi, 2008), or the configurations proposed for the Fiora Valley and the Marta basin (di Gennaro and Guidi, 2000).

Overall, RMCA IIB emerges as a phase of socio-political maturity: a landscape no longer shaped by transformation, but by the reproduction of a hierarchical or federative order that had already proven effective. In this sense, the phase represents a plateau, in which territorial saturation and institutional stability together underpin the long-term persistence of the political geography into the subsequent periods.

RMCA III (800-725 BCE): stability of principles, complexity of outcomes

The RMCA III phase (Fig 28) marks a perceptible attenuation of the model's discriminative power relative to RMCA IIA and IIB, while preserving the same underlying settlement logic. For the "site" class, Precision remains high (0.80), indicating that most locations predicted as settlements are true sites, whereas Sensitivity/Recall drops to 0.57, revealing a substantial increase in false negatives. The resulting F-measure (0.67) points to a less balanced trade-off between selectivity and sensitivity than in the preceding phases. With 10 correct classifications out of 14 cases, overall accuracy is approximately 0.71, corresponding to a

moderate agreement beyond chance. From a modelling perspective, this pattern indicates that the core locational rules remain selective but are no longer sufficient to capture the full diversity of settlement situations emerging in this phase.

This shift is nevertheless embedded within a stable hierarchy of predictors. Both mean SHAP values and normalized split frequencies continue to identify topographic setting as the dominant driver of settlement location. Its mean SHAP contribution (0.122) is again by far the highest among all variables, and its split frequency reaches the maximum value (1.0), confirming that morphologically distinctive positions remain the principal attractors for site establishment. By contrast, hydrological variables (rivers, springs, sea, water bodies) are still frequently used to structure the forest (split frequencies between 0.65 and 0.92), yet their SHAP contributions are close to zero or slightly negative, indicating a largely contextual or exclusionary role rather than a positive pull on settlement choice. Altitude shows only a marginal positive effect, reinforcing the interpretation that elevation acts mainly through its coupling with topographic configuration.

Taken together, these metrics suggest that RMCA III does not represent a relaxation of the dominant settlement drivers, but rather a phase in which a well-established topographic logic coexists with an increasingly diversified set of site functions and roles. The persistence of high precision indicates that the model still defines a narrow and socially regulated core niche, whereas the marked decline in recall reflects the growing number of sites that fall outside this core pattern. In socio-economic terms, this is consistent with a landscape that has reached, or is very close to, full territorial saturation: once most viable and strategic locations were already occupied, further developments could only proceed through internal differentiation, reorganisation, and the emergence of functionally specialised or hierarchically distinct sites within an already filled framework (Fig 29).

A particularly illuminating example is provided by the coastal site of Piscina Torta (Alessandri et al., 2024, 2023; Attema et al., 2025). Here, between the mid-eighth and the sixth century BCE, salt was very likely produced using the briquetage technique, a process requiring large quantities of seawater, fuel wood, and clay for the serial production of disposable ceramic containers, as well as proximity to a brackish lagoon from which naturally enriched brine could be obtained. The location of Piscina Torta near the terminal sector of the reconstructed Ostia lagoon was therefore dictated by the co-occurrence of these specific constraints. Such a choice clearly departs from the consolidated criteria governing residential settlement, dominated by topographic setting, and thus tends to elude the model's predictions, lowering sensitivity/recall. At the same time, it provides compelling evidence that ecological niches were increasingly being occupied for purposes other than habitation.

In this sense, RMCA III captures a stage in which the political landscape forged in earlier phases remains structurally intact, but becomes spatially more complex and articulated. Settlement placement continues to be anchored to topographic prominence, yet the increasing mismatch between the dominant pattern and the full set of occupied sites signals a system under pressure from demographic growth, urban expansion, and the diversification of socio-political roles. The reduced predictive completeness of the model thus mirrors a historical reality in which stability of principles coexisted with growing complexity of outcomes, marking the transition from a canalised protohistoric landscape to the more heterogeneous spatial organisation of the early historical period.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates the value of Random Forest modelling, coupled with explainable AI techniques, as an exploratory framework for investigating long-term settlement dynamics in protohistoric landscapes. Rather than aiming at predictive mapping, the approach has been used here to disentangle the relative and diachronic importance of environmental factors shaping settlement choices. The combination of normalized

split frequencies and SHAP values proved particularly informative: the former capturing the structural role of variables in partitioning the feature space, the latter quantifying the magnitude and direction of their contribution to site prediction. Together, these metrics allowed us to identify both stable predictors and phase-specific shifts, while also highlighting situations in which variables act primarily as exclusionary or contextual filters. At the same time, the analysis exposes clear limitations. The reliance on pseudo-absence points, the small number of sites in several phases, and the inherent spatial and taphonomic biases of the archaeological record inevitably constrain the robustness of performance metrics and the generalisability of results. In this sense, the Random Forest models should not be read as optimal classifiers, but as heuristic devices that amplify recurrent patterns in complex, noisy data and make them accessible to critical archaeological interpretation.

Within these limits, the modelling results reveal a coherent long-term transformation in the environmental logic of settlement. From the Early and early Middle Bronze Age, when hydrological accessibility dominated the discrimination between sites and non-sites, the system progressively reweighted towards topographic structure as the principal axis of differentiation. From MBA3 onwards, and especially from FBA12 through the RMCA phases, morphologically distinctive and elevated settings emerged as the dominant attractors, producing increasingly canalised and statistically separable settlement signatures. This diachronic shift from hydrologically anchored to topographically anchored settlement patterns is not merely an environmental trend, but reflects a deeper transformation in the social use of space, in which defensibility, visibility, and positional control became central to the organisation of inhabited landscapes.

Read from a historical perspective, the model captures the gradual emergence, consolidation, and eventual stabilisation of a politically structured landscape in Latium Vetus. The exploratory and weakly differentiated patterns of the early phases give way, in MBA3, to the first coherent structuring of territory around defensible nodes. During the Recent and Final Bronze Age, this framework is progressively saturated and formalised, in parallel with growing social differentiation, the institutionalisation of inequality, and the appearance of elite lineages anchored to key places. In the RMCA phases, this logic crystallises into a mature territorial order, in which settlement placement becomes a normative and socially regulated act embedded within hierarchical or federative systems. The later decline in recall observed in RMCA III does not indicate a breakdown of this logic, but rather its coexistence with increasing functional diversification, as specialised sites, such as coastal salt-production centres like Piscina Torta, occupy ecological niches defined by economic constraints rather than residential norms. In this sense, the growing mismatch between dominant locational rules and the full range of occupied sites mirrors a landscape likely under pressure from territorial saturation, demographic growth, and socio-political complexity.

Overall, the integration of Random Forest modelling with archaeological interpretation offers a powerful means to bridge ecological constraints and historically contingent choices. By making explicit the shifting dimensions along which settlements differ from their surroundings, the approach provides a quantitative backbone to long-standing qualitative narratives about the rise of defensible centres, territorial control, and early political organisation in central Italy. More broadly, this study illustrates how explainable machine learning can serve not as a substitute for archaeological reasoning, but as a complementary lens through which complex spatial histories can be explored, tested, and refined.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author used OpenAI ChatGPT 5.1 in order to translate text from and into English and to improve the clarity and readability of the English manuscript. After using these tools, the

author carefully reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the final version of the publication.

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Captions

Fig 1: Study area. Coordinates expressed in WGS 84 UTM zone 33N (EPSG:32633). Background, elaborated by the author from TinItaly dataset (Tarquini S., I. Isola, M. Favalli, A. Battistini, G. Dotta, 2023. TINITALY, a digital elevation model of Italy with a 10 meters cell size (Version 1.1). Istituto Nazionale di

Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV). <https://doi.org/10.13127/tinality/1.1>). The dataset is published with a CC BY 4.0 license (downloaded from https://tinality.pi.ingv.it/Download_Area1_1.html). Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 2: Overview of Archaeological Research Across Latium Vetus. The distribution of systematic surveys and Forma Italiae (FI) volumes covers diverse landscape units (volcanic, coastal, and plain), ensuring environmental representativeness. Reconstructed shoreline for the Bronze and Iron Ages as determined by Alessandri 2013. Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org). 1 (Bietti Sestieri, 1984; Bietti Sestieri and Sebastiani, 1986); 2 (Mari, 1983); 3 (Mari, 1991); 4 (Quilici, 1974); 5 (Muzzioli, 1970); 6 (De Rossi, 1967); 7 (De Rossi, 1979); 8 (Valenti, 2003); 9 (De Rossi, 1970); 10 (Morselli and Tortorici, 1982); 11 (Attema et al., 2002); 12 (Attema, 1993); 13 (Brandizzi Vittucci, 1968); 14 (Attema et al., 2010a); 15 (Attema et al., 2010b); 16 (Piccarreta, 1977)

Fig 3: Urbanized areas within the study area. Data derived from Table B of the PTPR (Regional Territorial Landscape Plan), downloaded from Open Data Lazio, and published under a CC-BY-4.0 license (<https://dati.lazio.it/dataset/ptpr-tav-b-urbanizzato/resource/4804835f-00ab-4671-8770-45d663ffcfd0>). Reconstructed shoreline for the Bronze and Iron Ages as determined by Alessandri 2013. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 4: Maps of absolute elevations (above sea level), distances from rivers, the sea, springs, water bodies and classes of landscape units. Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 5: Workflow and architecture of the Random Forest model implemented in KNIME (www.knime.com).

Fig 6: SHAP dependence plots for the main environmental variables in the Random Forest model: Altitude, distance from the sea, distance from water bodies, distance from rivers, distance from springs and topographic setting. Point colour encodes the earliest securely attested phase at each site. The dashed blue line marks SHAP = 0, and the red line shows the LOESS trend (frac = 0.5).

Fig 7: SHAP dependence plots for the soil classes in the Random Forest model: C1-6. Point colour encodes the earliest securely attested phase at each site. The dashed blue line marks SHAP = 0, and the red line shows the LOESS trend (frac = 0.5).

Fig 8: Importance of environmental variables across chronological phases. Variable importance based on normalized split frequencies in the Random Forest

Fig 9: Trend of normalized split frequencies across the chronological phases, geomorphologic parameters

Fig 10: Trend of normalized split frequencies across the chronological phases, soil parameters

Fig 11: Phase by phase mean SHAP values for the real settlement positive outcome

Fig 12: Trend of mean SHAP values for the real settlement positive outcome across the chronological phases, geomorphologic parameters

Fig 13: Trend of mean SHAP values for the real settlement positive outcome across the chronological phases, soil parameters

Fig 14: Phase map with Early Bronze Age settlements. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 15: Phase map with Middle Bronze Age settlements, subphases 1 and 2. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 16: Phase map with Middle Bronze Age settlements, subphase 3. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 17: Phase map with Middle Bronze Age settlements, subphase 3. The sites are classified according to their topographic setting into two groups: those occupying more readily defensible positions, and those situated in more open settings. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 18: Phase map with Recent Bronze Age settlements. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 19: Phase map with Recent Bronze Age settlements. The sites are classified according to their topographic setting into two groups: those occupying more readily defensible positions, and those situated in more open settings. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 20: Phase map with Final Bronze Age settlements, subphases 1 and 2. For clarity, the site of Casale Nuovo, situated just beyond the boundaries of the study area, has been included. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 21: Phase map with Final Bronze Age settlements, subphases 1 and 2. The sites are classified according to their topographic setting into two groups: those occupying more readily defensible positions, and those situated in more open settings. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 22: Phase map with Final Bronze Age settlements, subphase 3 (also known as Roma Colli Albani, subphase I). Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 23: Phase map with Final Bronze Age settlements, subphase 3. The sites are classified according to their topographic setting into two groups: those occupying more readily defensible positions, and those situated in more open settings. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 24: Phase map with Roma Colli Albani facies settlements, subphase IIA. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 25: Phase map with Roma Colli Albani facies settlements, subphase IIA. The sites are classified according to their topographic setting into two groups: those occupying more readily defensible positions, and those situated in more open settings. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 26: Phase map with Roma Colli Albani facies settlements, subphase IIB. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 27: Phase map with Roma Colli Albani facies settlements, subphase IIB. The sites are classified according to their topographic setting into two groups: those occupying more readily defensible positions, and those situated in more open settings. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 28: Phase map with Roma Colli Albani facies settlements, subphase III. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Fig 29: Phase map with Roma Colli Albani facies settlements, subphase III. The sites are classified according to their topographic setting into two groups: those occupying more readily defensible positions, and those situated in more open settings. Site locations, reconstructed shoreline and lakes/lagoons as determined by Alessandri (2013). Background, see Fig 1. Map created with QGIS 3.40, (www.qgis.org).

Appendix A.: Soil classes

S1 Table: Environmental and classification data used in the Random Forest model. The table reports site ID, altitude (m a.s.l.), distances from sea, rivers, water bodies, and springs (in walking seconds/100), surface areas of soil classes C1–C6 (m²), and settlement classification (Yes = real settlement, No = simulated location).

S2 Table: Parameter optimization settings for the Random Forest model in KNIME.

S4 Table: Score matrix of the Random Forest models between settlements and pseudo-absence points.

S5 Table: SHAP values for individual cases (only real settlements and prediction=Yes) in the Random Forest model.

S6 Table: Mean SHAP values by chronological phase (only real settlements and prediction=Yes).

S7 Table: Soil descriptions. The official descriptions are in Italian. The English translation has been provided by the author.

Fig 1

Fig. 2

Id	Survey
1	Preistoria e protostoria nel territorio di Roma
2	FI Tibur III
3	FI Tibur IV
4	FI Collatia
5	FI Praeneste II
6	FI Tellenae
7	FI Bovillae
8	FI Ager Tusculanus
9	FI Apiolae
10	FI Ardea
11	Lanuvio Survey (GIA)
12	Cisterna Survey (GIA)
13	FI Cora
14	Regional Pathways to Complexity (GIA)
15	Nettuno and Astura Survey (GIA)
16	FI Astura

Coordinate: WGS 84, UTM 33N, EPSG 32633

Fig. 3

Fig. 5

Fig.6

Fig.7

Normalized split frequencies

EBA	1.00	0.82	0.70	0.64	0.57	0.55	0.52	0.50	0.45	0.43	0.34	0.02
MBA12	1.00	0.74	0.71	0.61	0.56	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.48	0.44	0.29	0.10
MBA3	1.00	0.93	0.78	0.63	0.61	0.54	0.44	0.39	0.36	0.34	0.28	0.05
RBA	1.00	0.92	0.80	0.79	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.62	0.60	0.54	0.49	0.32
FBA12	1.00	0.98	0.96	0.90	0.83	0.83	0.79	0.78	0.73	0.65	0.46	0.27
FBA3	1.00	0.78	0.73	0.72	0.66	0.65	0.60	0.59	0.56	0.55	0.44	0.38
RMCAIIA	1.00	0.93	0.75	0.63	0.59	0.58	0.56	0.51	0.51	0.46	0.29	0.29
RMCAIIB	1.00	0.59	0.57	0.57	0.56	0.48	0.48	0.45	0.43	0.35	0.32	0.27
RMCAIII	1.00	0.92	0.91	0.73	0.72	0.66	0.65	0.63	0.62	0.62	0.58	0.56
ALL	1.00	0.98	0.93	0.88	0.75	0.73	0.59	0.56	0.56	0.49	0.40	0.39

Top setting

Rivers

Sea

Springs

Water bodies

Alt

C1

C2

C3

C4

C5

C6

Fig.8

Fig.9

Fig. 10

Fig. 11

Mean SHAP values

EBA	0,053	0,043	0,037	0,029	0,000	-0,001	-0,001	-0,005	-0,019	-0,020	-0,059	-0,090
MBA12	0,086	0,032	0,014	0,009	0,003	0,003	0,003	-0,001	-0,005	-0,007	-0,011	-0,031
MBA3	0,052	0,038	0,025	0,016	0,007	0,004	0,003	0,001	0,000	-0,004	-0,006	-0,009
RBA	0,026	0,016	0,011	0,007	0,007	-0,001	-0,002	-0,002	-0,012	-0,024	-0,027	-0,046
FBA12	0,112	0,032	0,032	0,016	0,011	0,010	0,006	0,004	0,004	-0,002	-0,009	-0,033
FBA3	0,127	0,020	0,015	0,014	0,005	0,001	0,001	0,001	-0,002	-0,003	-0,004	-0,004
RMCAIIA	0,135	0,016	0,013	0,007	0,005	0,003	0,003	0,002	0,000	-0,005	-0,010	-0,010
RMCAIIB	0,090	0,019	0,014	0,013	0,012	0,008	0,008	0,004	-0,002	-0,006	-0,015	-0,019
RMCAIII	0,122	0,008	0,004	-0,002	-0,003	-0,006	-0,007	-0,008	-0,013	-0,013	-0,013	-0,025
ALL	0,057	0,021	0,014	0,011	0,011	0,009	0,006	0,004	0,003	0,003	0,003	-0,002

Top. setting

Rivers

Sea

Springs

Water bodies

Alt

C1

C2

C3

C4

C5

C6

Fig. 12

Fig. 13

139	Fosso di Torre Spaccata
143	Casale di Torre Spaccata
144	Fosso della Torre
145	S. Maria
180	Area Stop 4
188	Osteria del Malpasso
193	Valle Porcina
220	CR1
32	Villaggio delle Macine
78	Colle Mattia
F19	Campidoglio
F23	Pian Quintino
L35	Quadraro

Fig. 14

111	Tenuta di Valleranello
112	Tenuta della Falcognana
113	Casali Mancini
178	Colle dell'Uomo Morto
179	San Giacomo
180	Area Stop 4
219	CR8e9
22	Lariano Campo Sportivo
220	CR1
32	Villaggio delle Macine
78	Colle Mattia
AB22	Torre Astura
AB24	Valdroni
F15	Lanuvio
F19	Campidoglio
F22	Palatino
F23	Pian Quintino
F6	Cacamele
F7	La Campana
L10	Colle Rotondo
L15	Fosso Foglino
L4A	Pratica di Mare
L8	Spiagge S. Lorenzo

Fig. 15

146	Castiglione
220	CR1
3	Colle dei Cappuccini
4	Colle della Mola
5	Colle dell'Asino
53	Pilozzo
54	Podere Scalette
56	Torre del Padiglione, nord
78	Colle Mattia
79	Colle S Andrea
F19	Campidoglio
F22	Palatino
F23	Pian Quintino
F7	La Campana
G49	Santa Maria
L10	Colle Rotondo
L1D	Ficana
L4A	Pratica di Mare
L4B	Pratica di Mare Santuario 13 Altari

Fig. 16

Fig. 17

122	Monte di Leva
124	Acqua Acetosa Laurentina
132	Torre di Mezzavia abitato
133	Quadrato, Osteria del Curato
135	Orti Poli
136	Tenuta di Torre Nova
20	Maschio dei Ferrari
214	Via Bianchi Bandinelli, abitato
220	CR1
29	Paluzzi
3	Colle dei Cappuccini
38	Castel Gandolfo ex Orti Torlonia
4	Colle della Mola
78	Colle Mattia
F10	Tuscolo
F19	Campidoglio
F22	Palatino
F24	Ardea
L10	Colle Rotondo
L19	Saracca
L1D	Ficana
L2	Ostia Antica Collettore
L3	Ostia Antica Terme di Nettuno
L4A	Pratica di Mare

Fig. 18

Fig. 19

121	Casale della Perna
122	Monte di Leva
124	Acqua Acetosa Laurentina
126	Torrino
132	Torre di Mezzavia abitato
133	Quadrato, Osteria del Curato
140	Casa Calda
166	La Rustica
180	Area Stop 4
181	Camposelva
20	Maschio dei Ferrari
214	Via Bianchi Bandinelli, abitato
215	Santuario di Diana
220	CR1
29	Paluzzi
3	Colle dei Cappuccini
4	Colle della Mola
42	Fontan Tempesta
50	Colle del Vescovo
AB20	Torre del Giglio
AB23A	Torre del Padiglione, sud
AB24	Valdroni
AB5	Bosco Nettuno
F10	Tuscolo
F19	Campidoglio
F22	Palatino
F24	Ardea
L10	Colle Rotondo
L11	Tor Caldara
L17	Le Grottacce
L18	Pelliccione
L1D	Ficana
L4A	Pratica di Mare
L7	Fosso della Bottaccia

Fig. 20

Fig. 21

11	Sorgente Preziosa
121	Casale della Perna
122	Monte di Leva
124	Acqua Acetosa Laurentina
126	Torrino
166	La Rustica
180	Area Stop 4
20	Maschio dei Ferrari
21	Colle dei Morti
214	Via Bianchi Bandinelli, abitato
215	Santuario di Diana
220	CR1
29	Paluzzi
3	Colle dei Cappuccini
36	Monte Savello
4	Colle della Mola
42	Fontan Tempesta
5	Colle dell'Asino
50	Colle del Vescovo
80	Monte Peschio
82	Colli della Coedra
AB20	Torre del Giglio
AB23A	Torre del Padiglione, sud
AB24	Valdroni
AB5	Bosco Nettuno
F10	Tuscolo
F19	Campidoglio
F2	Colonna
F22	Palatino
F24	Ardea
F25	Monte Cavo
F26	Prato della Corte
F27	Colle della Fragola
F5	Anzio
F9	Velletri
L10	Colle Rotondo
L11	Tor Caldara
L17	Le Grottaece
L1D	Ficana
L2	Ostia Antica Collettore
L4A	Pratica di Mare
L5E	Ardea, pendio meridionale
L7	Fosso della Bottaccia

Fig. 22

Fig. 23

194	Gabi
20	Maschio dei Ferrari
21	Colle dei Morti
23	Monte Castellaccio
29	Paluzzi
3	Colle dei Cappuccini
36	Monte Savello
40	Via dei Laghi Mimose
41	Divin Maestro
50	Colle del Vescovo
80	Monte Peschio
82	Colli della Coedra
F10	Tuscolo
F13	Cisterna
F15	Lanuvio
F19	Campidoglio
F2	Colonna
F22	Palatino
F24	Ardea
F25	Monte Cavo
F26	Prato della Corte
F5	Anzio
F9	Velletri
G29	Coste Caselle
G49	Santa Maria
L10	Colle Rotondo
L14C	Satricum
L1D	Ficana
L4A	Pratica di Mare

Fig. 24

Fig. 25

104	Castel di Decima abitato
124	Acqua Acetosa Laurentina
16	Valle Viola
164	Antemnae
194	Gabi
20	Maschio dei Ferrari
23	Monte Castellaccio
29	Paluzzi
3	Colle dei Cappuccini
30	Pescaccio
38	Castel Gandolfo ex Orti Torlonia
40	Via dei Laghi Mimose
41	Divin Maestro
82	Colli della Coedra
F1	Ariccia
F10	Tuscolo
F13	Cisterna
F15	Lanuvio
F19	Campidoglio
F2	Colonna
F22	Palatino
F24	Ardea
F25	Monte Cavo
F26	Prato della Corte
F5	Anzio
F9	Velletri
L10	Colle Rotondo
L14C	Satricum
L1D	Ficana
L4A	Pratica di Mare
L4B	Pratica di Mare Santuario 13 Altari
L6	L'Altare

Fig. 26

Fig. 27

104	Castel di Decima abitato
124	Acqua Acetosa Laurentina
141	Casale De Luca
164	Antemnae
166	La Rustica
194	Gabi
20	Maschio dei Ferrari
23	Monte Castellaccio
29	Paluzzi
3	Colle dei Cappuccini
38	Castel Gandolfo ex Orti Torlonia
401	Piscina Torta
50	Colle del Vescovo
82	Colli della Coedra
AB15	Loricina
F1	Ariccia
F10	Tuscolo
F13	Cisterna
F15	Lanuvio
F19	Campidoglio
F2	Colonna
F22	Palatino
F24	Ardea
F25	Monte Cavo
F26	Prato della Corte
F27	Colle della Fragola
F5	Anzio
F9	Velletri
L10	Colle Rotondo
L13	Nettuno
L14C	Satricum
L1D	Ficana
L4A	Pratica di Mare
L6	L'Altare

Fig. 28

Fig. 29